

Study of the Habits of Using Sanitary Pads among Students of Our College and Its Impact on Health & Environment Respectively

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Abstract

Today, the life is very fast. Every consumable product available in the market is of limited life – use it once and throw. The same is true for sanitary napkins. The young girls' mentality is to use it and throw. They never think about the product they use and throw. Proper attention is not given whether the product is good for her own health and whether disposing it would be hazardous from the viewpoint of public health and environment.

The girls, who are very conscious of their beauty, are not at all aware about their own health. Every month the girls and women have menstrual period. They use sanitary napkins, but they do not know which are good for their health and safe for environment after disposing it. Our objective is to give information to our students about good sanitary napkins for their health and environment.

Key words, Habits of using sanitary pads, Awareness about health problems due to use of sanitary pads, environmental problems due to improper disposal, try to provide an alternative solution to the Students about eco-friendly sanitary napkins.

Introduction

Every day, the sun rises with a lot of Questions. The times are changing very fast but certainly we are witnessing a wind of changes blowing all over the world in all spheres of life.

Our college is a women's college. The students of our college are a part of this change. They feel that every consumable product available in the market has the limited life, use it once and throw. Here students approach is like we are modern. Modernization and progress has had its share of disadvantages. Sanitary napkins are no exceptions to this. The mentality of the young generation is to use and throw without any consideration to what product they use or what do they throw in the environment. No proper attention is given whether the product is good for her own health or the hazard to the public health and surroundings after its disposal. It will pollute land, water, air.

Our college is located in CENTRAL MUMBAI, and it is affiliated to the SNDT University. We have (7000) seven thousand girl students, ladies as teaching and non teaching staff. It is surprising that the girl students who are very conscious about their beauty are not at all aware about their own health aspects. Every month, the girls and women have menstrual periods. They use sanitary napkins. But they do not know which product is good for their own health, as well as, safe for environment after its disposal.

Very important facts from study:

Menstrual Cycles in a woman's lifetime is for approximately 35 years;

A Woman on an average may have 400 or more periods in her lifetime;

Widely used menstrual sanitary protections – Pads & Tampons (absorbents);

Pad and Tampons are prone to allergies, rashes, TSS (Toxic Shock syndrome);

Higher absorbency pad / tampon purely allow longer between changes but poses risks and more problems with your body's natural moisture levels and self cleaning mechanisms;

On an average a woman would use 10,000-12,000 pads / tampons in her lifetime;

12,000 pads on an average amounts to approximately 250 Cubic feet of landfill;

1 used pad takes hundreds of years to decompose since not easily bio degradable;

72% of blocked drains are caused by flushing of used sanitary protections;

In 2007, India had a consumption of approximately 2,66,00,00,000 sanitary pads;

Hypothesis

- 1) To bring awareness among students about environmental hazards caused due to disposal of sanitary pads.
- 2) To sensitize them to use to the eco friendly products during menstruation

Objectives

- 1) To study the existing level of knowledge and practices regarding menstruation among adolescent college girls and to assess the change in knowledge level and practices after health education on menstruation and healthy menstrual practises.
- 2) To assess the source of information, beliefs, misconceptions and restrictions related to menstruation.
- 3) To educate the students about the hazards to environment after improper disposal/ throwing of sanitary pads.

Methodology

The community based interventional study was conducted among 100 girl students of class 11 to TYBA from a college in Matunga, Mumbai.

We structured questionnaire in Marathi and English. It included topics concerning menstruation, sources of information, menstrual hygiene, beliefs, health problems during menstruation and environmental problems after disposing the sanitary pads.

Doctors also were interviewed, to find the health problems to the patients due to use of sanitary pads.

Lady peons also were interviewed to know how do they dispose the pads, clean the toilets, collect sanitary pads and the problems face therein, their level of awareness about environmental problems caused by disposal of sanitary pads.

Later an adhesive strip was placed on the bottom of the pad for attachment to the saddle of the panties, and this became a favoured method with women.

An average woman throws away 125 to 150 kgs of tampons panel and applicators in her lifetime. The great majority of these end up in landfills or something the sewage treatment plants must deal with. Plastic pads applicators from sewage outfalls are one of the most common forms of trash on beaches. For building owners, pads and tampons that are flushed down the toilet are the most common cause of plumbing problems.

Findings And Discussion

Most of the girls get menarche from 11 to 15 yrs of age. They received information from various sources. This survey conducted by many points to the fact that 78% girls got information and even orientation about menstruation before the onset from their mothers; 18% of the girls got from friends and 11% got from the school.

70% of the girls use sanitary pads, 22% use cloth pads and only 8% use cotton. They were of the opinion that sanitary pads are very convenient to use as women in today's world have to be out of their houses for long hours.

30% of the girls who didn't use sanitary pads because 16% found it expensive to use and 7% didn't find it satisfactory. 7% of the girl students were hesitant to use the product owing to the fear of vaginal infection and rashes. 49% suffer from health problems during menstruation. 11% feel uncomfortable during this phase. 36% of girl students suffer from abdominal pains and 6% girl students complained about white discharge. Since we get girl student from poor socio-economic background, they do not get proper nutrition, thereby suffering by anaemia. They are not aware and even their families do not encourage them to consult doctors for the same. Their food habits are very poor and they consider it as a social taboo to discuss this freely with the doctors, friends or others. 56% girls suggested for all time availability

of pads in the college. 30% wished to get medicines for menstrual pains. 47% demanded well-disposed machines for sanitary disposal; 25% asked for proper water facilities. 67% girls requested for special dustbins for disposal. 59% demanded clean toilets and 27% asked for separate rooms for this purpose.

Menstrual Waste Disposal

The general practice that people are comfortable with is to dispose of menstruation waste in toilets or rubbish bins. Some also prefer burning them. The rural women respondents usually rinse the blood first before disposing. The reason behind this is the belief that blood is sacred and it should not be left around in the open.

The disposal of menstruation protection seems to be influenced by location. Women dispose of this differently depending on where they are at the time. For instance, their behavior when they are at home is different than when they are in public places. When in public places, the behavior of rural people who are accustomed to throwing products in the pit, changes according to the toilet type used. For instance, when they are in a place using flush toilets, they flush the products in the toilet. When it does not flush, they take it out, wrap it with toilet paper and throw it in the dustbin inside the toilet. There are those who also say that they wrap it and carry it home with them and dispose it in their pit toilets. In the suburbs and formal townships, the common behavior seems to be throwing them in the bin or flushing them down the toilet and sometimes it gets burned when at home.

When asked about environmental hazards 74% girls thought disposing of sanitary pads is a big environmental hazard. 14% girls are not aware about the hazards caused by the environment.

During menstruation, 85% of the girls use home toilets and 43% use public toilets. They said since they had to remain out for longer period of time and moreover due to heavy flow at times, were compelled to use public toilets. 87% didn't attend college during menstruation as we can see from the earlier data that 85% of the girls student prefer to use only home toilets. 13% girls come to attend the lectures.

Impact of sanitary protections on the environment

Over 90% of a sanitary pad is made of crude oil plastic; the rest is made from chlorine-bleached wood pulp. If you think about the impact on our environment of making the absorbent material that fills out the pad, which includes chopping down large areas of forests to source the wood and then chlorine bleaching the pulp, the use of crude oil plastic is a massive burden on the environment. We are rightly concerned about the billion plastic shopping bags given away daily, but by using plastic

laden feminine hygiene products, each year we add the equivalent of 180 billion plastic bags to our waste stream.

According to the Algalita Marine Research Foundation, 80% of the plastic floating in our oceans comes from land as waste under 5mm passes through the filters and enters our streams, rivers, oceans and the stomachs of birds, fishes and other wildlife. If plastic is burnt in an incinerator, it will release dioxin into the air that we all need to breathe, and will eventually go on to also pollute the water we need to drink and the soil that we depend on to grow our food.

According to Japanese specialist Rie Ito, "Disposal sanitary napkins are bleached with chlorine may cause cancer and vestigial chlorine can cause irritation and allergic reactions to women".

They found that the main environmental impact of the products was in fact caused by the processing of raw materials, particularly LDPE (low density polyethelene) – or the plastics used in the backing of pads and tampon applicators, and cellulose production. As production of these plastics requires a lot of energy and creates long lasting waste, the main impact from the life cycle of these products is fossil fuel use, though the waste produced is significant in its own right. In a choice between pads and tampons, pads have more of an environmental impact due to their plastic components. It's essentially the feminine hygiene version of "paper or plastic?"

That isn't to say that tampons don't also have a significant environmental impact. The cotton fiber used in the production of tampons contributes 80% of their total impact. The processing is resource intensive as the farming of cotton requires large amounts of water, pesticides and fertilizer. And while they do not last indefinitely, like the plastic liners used in pads, tampons still take about six months to biodegrade according to Liz Sutton of the Women's Environmental Network. Really, it's the plastic applicators that are a problem. In 2009, The Ocean Conservancy's International Coastal Cleanup project collected 20,000 tampon applicators out of 4 million total pieces of reclaimed plastic waste. It can take applicators 25 years to break down in the ocean. Once they are broken down, they are often ingested by marine life causing digestion blockage and death. In fact, if it's an option – go ahead and throw the whole thing away rather than flushing. The cotton is often the cause of plumbing problems at home (around 70%) and at the treatment plant where they are removed as solid waste and sent to landfills anyway.

Modernization and progress has had its share of disadvantages and one of the main aspects of concern is the pollution it is causing to the earth-belt land, air and water. With increase in the global

population and the rising demand for the food and other essentials, there has been a rise in the amount of waste being generated daily by each one. This waste is ultimately thrown into environment and it can cause serious impacts on health problems.

In today's modern era, women have become career oriented. Due to the fast pace of today's life, the woman has very little time and a lot of things to do. To balance this see-saw of time and activities, she is forced to use many use-and-throw product options. The same is true even for her personal health and hygiene. During menstrual period, women find it convenient to use disposable sanitary pads. Now a days, a variety of products are available in the market, with different shapes, sizes, colours and materials such as gel. These sanitary pads are 'single-use and-throw' products. These cannot be use many times, since they cannot be washed or cleaned. These pads have to be disposed properly. Improper disposal of the used pads lead to personal health problems as well as environmental problems, For example, throwing the pads in open may lead to spread of diseases, or disposing them in public sewage causes choking up of sewage pipes, also causing in balance in the water-ecosystem. If dumped in the ground, the used sanitary pad provides very good breeding place for many bacteria which are already present in the air / ground. After breeding, these bacteria are thrown back in to the air, thus a major risk to the public health.

During our research in our college, we found that 42% of the students dispose the pads by flushing in the toilets. This causes choking up of the pipeline. 27% students throw the pads in dustbin which in turn, results growth and accumulation of bacteria on the toilet walls, dustbins etc. This also may lead to health problems to both, the students as well as the lady peon who cleans dustbins and the toilets.

The napkins are finally collected by the MCGM workers, and dumped in to dumping ground, without any precaution. These pads are not biodegradable, hence remain in dumping ground for year, creating health problems.

The girl students are aware of the environmental problems due to improper disposal. But they have no suitable alternative of safe method of disposing the pad; hence, they are forced to dispose the pads improperly.

Conclusion

Health is an environmental issue, so these issues shouldn't be overlooked. The chlorine bleaching process that is used to make these products look "cleaner" or more sanitary produces dioxin, the toxin of Agent Orange and Love Canal fame, which builds up in the fat cells of our bodies over time. Products that contain rayon also carry trace amounts of dioxin. While the FDA and Health Canada both state that the health risk is negligible, Dr. Philip

Tierno of New York University Medical Center says that while trace quantities of dioxin found in tampons aren't in and of themselves the issue, it's the overall exposure and build up that the use of chlorine-bleached and rayon based tampons adds to that's the problem. Some women are wary of tampons in general as all brands come tagged with warnings about TSS, or toxic shock syndrome, a rare but serious health condition which can occur in women who use super-absorbent or synthetic tampons. While organic cotton tampons / pads may solve the issue of pesticides and bleach, they still inevitably cause waste.

The green favourite being, of course, the menstrual cup. Proud to mention here that India has kept its pace with the global trend and has its own menstrual cup being sold internationally.

Poor sanitation is correlated with absenteeism and drop-out of girls in developing countries. But the efforts in school and college sanitation to address this issue have ignored menstrual management in latrine design and construction. Wider aspects of the issue such as privacy, water availability and awareness-raising amongst boys and men remain largely unexplored by development initiatives.

Hygiene promotion efforts have recently initiated a focus on this area but mainly on the software aspects i.e. telling girls and women about correct practices. These efforts do not currently target men and adolescent boys, nor do they systematically inform infrastructure design.

Minimal effort has gone into production and social marketing of low-cost napkins, reusable materials, research into bio-degradable, etc. Research and development efforts have been limited to commercial ventures that even today are unable to market products that are affordable for the poorest of the poor.

Disposal of napkins is absent from waste management training, infrastructure design and impact evaluation. In short, Menstrual Management is missing from the literature whether it be manuals to sensitize engineers to gender needs or technical manuals on latrine designs, sanitation for secondary schools, solid waste issues composting, bio-degradable materials or even simple training modules for health and sanitary workers.

At the college level, we arranged guest lectures and workshops to sensitize the students about this hazard. Workshops on "SAVE NATURE" were organised wherein the alternatives to the sanitary pads were introduced. The students were motivated to use the eco-friendly products like She-Cup. Most of them would not mind using product which is eco-friendly and Re-usable and is the need of the hour, given the Environmental Hazards caused by the napkins.

Call For Action

Having understood the scenario, we would like to offer some suggestions.

1. The students should clean the napkins before disposal.
2. The management of the college should install an incinerator so that the pads could be burnt.
3. The best way to minimise problems to the health as well as environment, is use homemade eco-friendly napkins. We wish to create awareness in this regard, among our students.
4. Training and interpersonal communication material, reading module and a flip book on menstrual hygiene can be developed and shared with the students in vernacular languages. Sanitary napkins should be sold at a uniform selling price in markets by the companies.

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